

INTUITIONISTIC FUZZY TRANSLATION OF BV- ALGEBRAS

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Cite This Article: A. Alphonse Anitha, Dr. M. Mary Jansi Rani & Dr. S. Katrin Lydia, "Intuitionistic Fuzzy Translation of BV - Algebras", International Journal of Advanced Trends in Engineering and Technology, Volume 6, Issue 2, Page Number

38-41, 2021.

Abstract:

In this paper, we introduced the concept of Intuitionistic Fuzzy translations to Intuitionistic Fuzzy BV-Algebras. We investigated some of their properties in detail by using the concepts of Intuitionistic fuzzy BV-Ideal and Intuitionistic fuzzy BV-subalgebra.

Key Words: BV-Algebras, Intuitionistic Fuzzy α –translation, Intuitionistic fuzzy BV–Ideal, Intuitionistic Fuzzy BV-Subalgebra.

1. Introduction:

L. A. Zadeh was introduced the concept of fuzzy set in 1965 [3]. Several researchers explored at the generalization of the perception of fuzzy subset. Atanassov was introduced the concept "Intuitionistic fuzzy set". Y. Imai and K. Iseki [1] introduced the concept of BCK/BCI algebras in 1978. K.Iseki [2] newly developed the concept of BCI-algebras in 1980. Kim C B and Kim H S [8], developed the new concept of BG-algebras in 2008. T. Priya and T. Ramachandran [4] [5] developed the class of PS-algebras, which is a generalization of BCI/BCK/Q /KU/d algebras. A. Prasanna, M. Premkumar and S. Ismail Mohideen [10], introduced the concept of fuzzy translation and multiplication on B-algebras in 2018. In Ho Hwang, Yong Lin Liu and Hee Sik Kim [6] introduced the concept of BV-Algebras. Tapan Senapati [11], discussed Translations of Intuitionistic Fuzzy B-algebras in 2015. In this paper, we introduced the concept of Intuitionistic fuzzy translation on BV-algebras and Intuitionistic fuzzy BV-subalgebra and Intuitionistic fuzzy BV-ideals of BV- algebras established some of its properties in detail.

2. Preliminaries:

In this section the basic definition of a BV-algebra, fuzzy BV-subalgebra, fuzzy BV-ideal, intuitionistic fuzzy set are recalled.

Definition 2.1: [5, 6]

An algebra $(A, *, 0)$ is said to be a BV-algebra if it satisfies

- (i) $x * x = 0$,
- (ii) $x * 0 = x$,
- (iii) $(x * y) * z = (0 * y) * (z * x)$ for all $x, y, z \in A$.

Example 2.1.1: [5, 6]

Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a set with the following table:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	1	3	2
1	1	0	2	3
2	2	3	0	1
3	3	2	1	0

Then it is easy to see that $(A, *, 0)$ is a BV-algebra.

Definition 2.2: [10]

A binary relation " \leq " on an BV-algebra A defined as $x \leq y$ if and only if $x * y = 0$.

Definition 2.3: [10]

Let S be non-empty subset of a BV-Algebra A , then S is called a BV–sub-algebra of A , if $x * y \in S \forall x, y \in S$

Definition 2.4: [4, 6]

Let A be a BV-Algebra and I be a subset of A , then I is called a BV-ideal of A if it satisfies following conditions:

- (i) $0 \in I$
- (ii) $x * y \in I$ and $y \in I \Rightarrow x \in I$

Definition 2.5: [4]

Let A be a BV-Algebra. Then a fuzzy set δ in A is defined as $\delta = \{\langle x, \delta(x) \rangle | x \in A\}$, where $\delta(x)$ is known as membership value of x in A and $0 \leq \delta(x) \leq 1$

Definition 2.6: [11]

Let A be a BV-Algebra. A fuzzy set I in A is called a fuzzy BV-ideal of A if it satisfies following conditions:

- (i) $\delta(0) \geq \delta(x)$
- (ii) $\delta(x) \geq \min\{\delta(y * x), \delta(y)\} \forall x, y \in A$

Definition 2.7: [11]

A fuzzy set δ in a BV-algebra A is called a fuzzy BV-subalgebra of A if $\delta(x * y) \geq \min\{\delta(x), \delta(y)\} \forall x, y \in A$

Definition 2.8: [11]

An Intuitionistic Fuzzy set A over X is an object having the form $A = \{(x, \gamma_A(x), \delta_A(x) | x \in X)\}$ where $\gamma_A: X \rightarrow [0,1]$ and $\delta_A: X \rightarrow [0,1]$ denoted the degree of membership and the degree of non-membership of x , respectively, with condition $0 \leq \gamma_A(x) + \delta_A(x) \leq 1 \forall x \in X$.

Definition 2.9: [11]

An Intuitionistic Fuzzy set A over X is called an intuitionistic fuzzy subalgebra of X if it satisfies

- (i) $\gamma_A(x * y) \geq \min\{\gamma_A(x), \gamma_A(y)\}$
- (ii) $\delta_A(x * y) \leq \max\{\delta_A(x), \delta_A(y)\} \forall x, y \in X$

Definition 2.10: [11]

An Intuitionistic Fuzzy set A over X is called an intuitionistic fuzzy ideal of X if it satisfies

- (i) $\gamma_A(0) \geq \gamma_A(x), \delta_A(0) \leq \delta_A(x)$,
- (ii) $\gamma_A(x) \geq \min\{\gamma_A(y * x), \gamma_A(y)\}$
- (iii) $\delta_A(x) \leq \max\{\delta_A(y * x), \delta_A(y)\} \forall x, y \in X$

3. Intuitionistic Fuzzy Translation of BV- Subalgebras and BV-Ideals: [6]

In this section, we introduced the notion of Intuitionistic Fuzzy translation of BV-algebras and some theorems on BV- subalgebras. If A denotes a intuitionistic fuzzy BV-algebra of X . An object for any fuzzy set δ of A , we denote $\mathcal{T} = \inf\{\delta_A(x) : x \in X\}$.

Definition 3.1:

Let δ be a subset of A and $\alpha \in [0, \mathcal{T}]$. An object having the form $A = \{(x, \gamma_A(x), \delta_A(x) | x \in X)\}$ where $\gamma_A: X \rightarrow [0,1]$ and $\delta_A: X \rightarrow [0,1]$ is said to be an intuitionistic fuzzy- α - translation of δ if it satisfies $(\gamma_A)_\alpha^T(x) = \gamma_A(x) + \alpha$ and $(\delta_A)_\alpha^T(x) = \delta_A(x) - \alpha \forall x \in A$.

Theorem 3.2:

For any intuitionistic fuzzy BV – algebra δ of A and $\alpha \in [0, \mathcal{T}]$, the intuitionistic fuzzy - α – translation $A_\alpha^T(x)$ of δ is a fuzzy intuitionistic BV – subalgebra of A .

Proof:

Let $x, y \in A$, and $\alpha \in [0, \mathcal{T}]$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Then } (\gamma_A)_\alpha^T(x * y) &= \gamma_A(x * y) + \alpha \\ &\geq \min\{\gamma_A(x), \gamma_A(y)\} + \alpha \\ &= \min\{\gamma_A(x) + \alpha, \gamma_A(y) + \alpha\} \\ &= \min\{(\gamma_A)_\alpha^T(x), (\gamma_A)_\alpha^T(y)\} \\ (\gamma_A)_\alpha^T(x * y) &\geq \min\{(\gamma_A)_\alpha^T(x), (\gamma_A)_\alpha^T(y)\} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Now } (\delta_A)_\alpha^T(x * y) &= \delta_A(x * y) - \alpha \\ &\leq \max\{\delta_A(x), \delta_A(y)\} - \alpha \\ &= \max\{\delta_A(x) - \alpha, \delta_A(y) - \alpha\} \\ &\geq \max\{(\delta_A)_\alpha^T(x), (\delta_A)_\alpha^T(y)\} \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof.

Theorem 3.3:

Let δ be an intuitionistic fuzzy subset of A such that the intuitionistic fuzzy - α – translation $A_\alpha^T(x)$ of δ is an intuitionistic fuzzy subalgebra of A , for some $\alpha \in [0, \mathcal{T}]$, then δ is an intuitionistic fuzzy BV – subalgebra of A .

Proof:

Let $x, y \in A$

Assume that $(\gamma_A)_\alpha^T(x)$ of δ is an intuitionistic fuzzy BV – subalgebra of A for $\alpha \in [0, \mathcal{T}]$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Then } \gamma_A(x * y) + \alpha &= (\gamma_A)_\alpha^T(x * y) \\ &= \min\{(\gamma_A)_\alpha^T(x), (\gamma_A)_\alpha^T(y)\} \\ &= \min\{\gamma_A(x) + \alpha, \gamma_A(y) + \alpha\} \\ &= \min\{\gamma_A(x), \gamma_A(y)\} + \alpha \\ \gamma_A(x * y) + \alpha &\geq \min\{\gamma_A(x), \gamma_A(y)\} + \alpha \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Now } \delta_A(x * y) - \alpha &= (\delta_A)_\alpha^T(x * y) \\ &\leq \max\{(\delta_A)_\alpha^T(x), (\delta_A)_\alpha^T(y)\} \\ &= \max\{\delta_A(x) - \alpha, \delta_A(y) - \alpha\} \\ &\leq \max\{\delta_A(x), \delta_A(y)\} - \alpha \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof.

Theorem 3.4:

If the intuitionistic fuzzy- α -translation $A_\alpha^T(x)$ of δ is an intuitionistic fuzzy BV-ideal of A, then it satisfies the condition $(\gamma_A)_\alpha^T(x * (y * x)) \geq (\gamma_A)_\alpha^T(y)$

Proof:

$$\begin{aligned} (\gamma_A)_\alpha^T(x * (y * x)) &= (\gamma_A)(x * (y * x)) + \alpha \\ &\geq \min\{(\gamma_A)(y * (x * (y * x))) + \alpha, ((\gamma_A)(y)) + \alpha\} \\ &\geq \min\{(\gamma_A)(0) + \alpha, (\gamma_A)(y) + \alpha\} \\ &\geq \min\{(\gamma_A)_\alpha^T(0), (\gamma_A)_\alpha^T(y)\} \\ (\gamma_A)_\alpha^T(x * (y * x)) &\geq (\gamma_A)_\alpha^T(y) \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 3.5:

If δ is an intuitionistic fuzzy BV-ideal of A, then the intuitionistic fuzzy- α -translation $A_\alpha^T(x)$ of δ is an intuitionistic fuzzy BV-ideal of A, for all $\alpha \in [0, \mathcal{I}]$

Proof:

Let δ is a fuzzy BV-ideal of A and let $\alpha \in [0, \mathcal{I}]$

Then (i) $(\gamma_A)_\alpha^T(0) = (\gamma_A)(0) + \alpha \geq (\gamma_A)(x) + \alpha = (\gamma_A)_\alpha^T(x)$
 $\Rightarrow \gamma_A(0) \geq \gamma_A(x)$

And $(\delta_A)_\alpha^T(0) = (\delta_A)(0) - \alpha \leq (\delta_A)(x) - \alpha = (\delta_A)_\alpha^T(x)$
 $\Rightarrow \delta_A(0) \leq \delta_A(x)$

(ii) $(\gamma_A)_\alpha^T(x) = (\gamma_A)(x) + \alpha$
 $\geq \min\{(\gamma_A)(y * x), (\gamma_A)(y)\} + \alpha$
 $\geq \min\{(\gamma_A)(y * x) + \alpha, (\gamma_A)(y) + \alpha\}$
 $\geq \min\{(\gamma_A)_\alpha^T(y * x), (\gamma_A)_\alpha^T(y)\}$

$\Rightarrow (\gamma_A)(x) \geq \min\{(\gamma_A)(y * x), (\gamma_A)(y)\}$

And $(\delta_A)_\alpha^T(x) = (\delta_A)(x) - \alpha$
 $\leq \max\{(\delta_A)(y * x), (\delta_A)(y)\} - \alpha$
 $\leq \max\{(\delta_A)(y * x) - \alpha, (\delta_A)(y) - \alpha\}$
 $\leq \max\{(\delta_A)_\alpha^T(y * x), (\delta_A)_\alpha^T(y)\}$

$\Rightarrow (\delta_A)(x) \leq \max\{(\delta_A)(y * x), (\delta_A)(y)\}$

Hence the intuitionistic fuzzy- α -translation $\delta_\alpha^T(x)$ of δ is an intuitionistic fuzzy BV-ideal of A, for all $\alpha \in [0, \mathcal{I}]$

Theorem 3.6:

Let δ be an intuitionistic fuzzy subset of A such that the intuitionistic fuzzy- α -translation $A_\alpha^T(x)$ of δ is an intuitionistic fuzzy BV-ideal of A, for some $\alpha \in [0, \mathcal{I}]$, then δ is an intuitionistic fuzzy BV-ideal of A.

Proof:

Assume that the intuitionistic fuzzy- α -translation $A_\alpha^T(x)$ of δ is an intuitionistic fuzzy BV-ideal of A, for some $\alpha \in [0, \mathcal{I}]$. Let $x, y \in A$.

Then (i) $(\gamma_A)(0) + \alpha = (\gamma_A)_\alpha^T(0) \geq (\gamma_A)_\alpha^T(x) = (\gamma_A)(x) + \alpha$
 $\Rightarrow (\gamma_A)(0) \geq (\gamma_A)(x)$

And $(\delta_A)(0) - \alpha = (\delta_A)_\alpha^T(0) \leq (\delta_A)_\alpha^T(x) = (\delta_A)(x) - \alpha$
 $\Rightarrow \delta_A(0) \leq \delta_A(x)$

(ii) $(\gamma_A)(x) + \alpha = (\gamma_A)_\alpha^T(x)$
 $\geq \min\{(\gamma_A)_\alpha^T(y * x), (\gamma_A)_\alpha^T(y)\}$
 $\geq \min\{(\gamma_A)(y * x) + \alpha, (\gamma_A)(y) + \alpha\}$
 $\geq \min\{(\gamma_A)(y * x), (\gamma_A)(y)\} + \alpha$

$(\gamma_A)(x) \geq \min\{(\gamma_A)(y * x), (\gamma_A)(y)\}$

And $(\delta_A)(x) - \alpha = (\delta_A)_\alpha^T(x)$
 $\leq \max\{(\delta_A)_\alpha^T(y * x), (\delta_A)_\alpha^T(y)\}$
 $\leq \max\{(\delta_A)(y * x) - \alpha, (\delta_A)(y) - \alpha\}$
 $\leq \max\{(\delta_A)(y * x), (\delta_A)(y)\} - \alpha$

$(\delta_A)(x) \leq \max\{(\delta_A)(y * x), (\delta_A)(y)\}$

Hence δ is an intuitionistic fuzzy BV-ideal of A.

4. Conclusion:

In this paper we have introduced the notion of intuitionistic fuzzy translation on BV-algebras through intuitionistic fuzzy BV-ideals. BV-algebras as another generalization of BCK/BCI/d/Q-Algebras. This concept can further be generalized to n-generated fuzzy sets, bipolar fuzzy set for new results in our future work.

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